

MICROMECHANICAL FAILURE ANALYSIS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER IN-PLANE AND TRANSVERSE SHEAR

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1 Introduction

With the increasing use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites in aerospace and other industries, the failure mechanisms of them should be well understood in order to take full advantage of their excellent performance and to develop even higher performance materials. However, as FRPs consist of heterogeneous materials, the interactions between the reinforcements and matrix as well as the interface make the failure process very complicated. Up to now the failure mechanisms of FRPs are not well revealed, and their strength cannot be accurately predicted. Generally, a full experimental approach is used to obtain their strengths, which requires a considerable amount of human, financial and time resources. Even so, as compared with the longitudinal properties, the experimental characterization of the properties in the transverse direction is subjected to more uncertainties and experimental data are actually scarcer. Therefore, an accurate and cost-effective method to reveal the damage initiation and evolution process of the composites and then to predict their strengths is urgently required. Previously, the authors [1] developed a micromechanical damage model by finite element method (FEM) to reveal the failure mechanisms and predict the strength of unidirectional FRP composites under transverse tension and compression, with some valuable conclusions obtained. However, the shear load has not been considered in the investigation, which may cause more complicated failure behavior. Though some researchers have carried out investigations on the micromechanical failure behavior of fiber reinforced composites under in-plane shear [2] and transverse shear [3][4], the failure mechanisms were

still not well revealed. Thus, this paper uses the presented micromechanical damage model to investigate the failure behavior of FRPs subjected to in-plane and transverse shear load. The stress-strain curves are obtained and compared with the experiment. The damage initiation and evolution process is discussed in detail, giving reasonable explanations to the failure mechanisms of the composite under both in-plane and transverse shear loads.

2 Simulation Strategies

2.1 Generation of RVE

To perform micromechanical analysis of composite material, a representative volume element (RVE) large enough to represent the bulk material should be constructed. LLorca et al [5] have proved that an RVE including 30 fibres is adequate to represent the macroscopic material, and this suggestion is adopted in our investigation. The RVE consists of three phases: the fibers, the matrix and the interface. It is well known that for FRPs the fibers are randomly distributed in the matrix, thus the RVE should take into account this characteristic. In our previous work [6], a novelty method named random sequential expansion (RSE) algorithm was proposed, which can overcome the jamming limit of hard-core model [7] to generate random fiber distributions for high value of fiber volume fraction (FVF). The RSE algorithm is used in this paper to generate the RVE of the composite material. The representative RVEs used for micromechanical analysis are shown in Fig.1, which contains 30 integrated fibers of 10 μm diameter, with FVF of 50% and 60%, respectively. The RVEs with 50% FVF are used for the transverse shear simulation, and those with 60% FVF for in-

plane shear simulation. In each case, five separate RVEs with different fiber distributions are generated

to take into account the effect of microscopic configuration.

Fig.1. The RVEs used for micromechanical analysis with fiber volume fraction of (a) 50% and (b) 60%

2.2 FEM model

FEM models are generated in ABAQUS/Explicit, which uses an explicit direct-integration procedure to overcome the convergence difficulty of numerical analysis. Plain strain models are used for transverse shear simulation, since the mechanical behavior in any transverse plane is basically the same for long fiber reinforced composite. While for in-plane shear simulation, three dimensional models must be adopted, as the load is along the fiber direction. The detailed description about the plain strain model can be found in [1], thus is not repeated here. For the three dimensional model, the fibers and matrix are meshed with 8-node linear brick element with reduced integration and hourglass control (C3D8R). A layer of 8-node three-dimensional cohesive elements (COH3D8) with very small thickness (0.01 μm) are inserted between each fiber and the surrounding matrix to simulate the interface. Shown in Fig.2 is the FEM model of one representative RVE with FVF of 60%. The whole model contains 228,200 elements.

Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the RVE to ensure continuity between neighboring RVEs, which are expressed by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{U}_1 &= \vec{u}(a, y, z) - \vec{u}(0, y, z) \\
 \vec{U}_2 &= \vec{u}(x, b, z) - \vec{u}(x, 0, z) \\
 \vec{U}_3 &= \vec{u}(x, y, c) - \vec{u}(x, y, 0)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

where *a*, *b* and *c* are dimensions of the RVE along the *x*, *y* and *z* axis direction, respectively.

Fig.2. 3-D FEM model of RVE

2.3 Material Models

The material is chosen from the World Wide Failure Exercise as E-glass/MY750/HY917/DY063 [8], with the properties of the fiber and matrix listed in Table 1.

As fiber failure is unlikely to happen under the current loadings, no damage model has been implemented for the fibres, which are modelled as linear elastic and transverse isotropic solids. On the other hand, experimental studies have shown that the dominant damage mechanisms involved in

transverse ply cracking of composites are matrix plastic deformation and interfacial debonding [9]. Therefore the failure behaviour of the polymeric matrix and the interface are introduced and discussed in detail as follows.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of the fiber and matrix

Fiber		Matrix	
Longitudinal modulus, E_{f1} (GPa)	74	Modulus, E_m (GPa)	3.35
Transverse modulus, E_{f2} (GPa)	74	Shear modulus, G_m (GPa)	1.24
In-plane shear modulus, G_{f12} (GPa)	30.8	Poisson's ratio, ν_m	0.35
Major Poisson's ratio, ν_{f12}	0.2	Tensile strength, σ_{mt} (MPa)	80
Transverse shear modulus, G_{f23}	30.8	Compressive strength, σ_{mc} (MPa)	120

2.3.1 Polymeric matrix

It is often observed that the behavior of polymers is sensitive to the hydrostatic stress [10][11]. To capture these characteristics, the extended linear Drucker-Prager yield criterion is employed, which is expressed by the following equation [12]:

$$F = t - p \tan \beta - d = 0, \quad t = \frac{1}{2}q \left[1 + \frac{1}{K} - \left(1 - \frac{1}{K} \right) \left(\frac{r}{q} \right)^3 \right] \quad (2)$$

where p is the hydrostatic stress, q is the Mises equivalent stress, r is the third invariant of deviatoric stress, β is the slope of the linear yield surface in the p - t stress plane, d is the cohesion of the material, and k is the ratio of the yield stress in triaxial tension to the yield stress in triaxial compression and, thus, introduces different yield behaviours between tension and compression.

The parameters needed for the numerical simulation, β , d and k , can be determined by the following equations [12]:

$$\tan \beta = \frac{6 \sin \phi}{3 - \sin \phi} \quad (3)$$

$$d = \left(1 - \frac{1}{3} \tan \beta \right) \sigma_{mc} \quad (4)$$

$$k = \frac{3 - \sin \phi}{3 + \sin \phi} \quad (5)$$

where, ϕ is the internal friction angle of the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion, which can be obtained from the tensile and compressive strength of the matrix [13]:

$$\sin \phi = \frac{\sigma_{mc} - \sigma_{mt}}{\sigma_{mc} + \sigma_{mt}} \quad (6)$$

Thus, it gives $\phi = 11.5^\circ$, and then we have $\beta = 23.2^\circ$, $d = 103$ MPa, $k = 0.875$.

Besides the yield criterion, there also should be a criterion for predicting the onset of damage. Experimental results indicate that the polymer shows rather brittle fracture behaviour at a very low strain in uniaxial tension, but it yields and shows considerable plastic deformation in uniaxial compression and pure shear [14]. Thus the criterion should be able to predict the damage onset discriminating between different triaxial stress states. This is achieved by the ductile criterion which assumes the equivalent plastic strain at the onset of damage $\bar{\epsilon}_D^{pl}$ to be a function of stress triaxiality η , where $\eta = -p/q$. The stress triaxiality is a measurement of the triaxial stress state, for example, η takes the value of zero under pure shear, and the values of $\pm 1/3$, $\pm 2/3$ and $\pm \infty$ for uniaxial, equibiaxial and equitriaxial tension and compression, respectively. In this paper, the equivalent plastic strains at the onset of damage for uniaxial tension and compression are set as 0.05 and 0.5, respectively, the reasonable values extracted from experimental results [14].

After the onset of failure, the damage evolution is controlled by a progressive failure procedure, the stress-strain behavior of which is illustrated in Fig.3. The dashed curve in the figure is the stress-strain response in the absence of damage, while the solid curve represents the damaged response. The damage manifests itself in two forms: softening of the yield stress and degradation of the elasticity, both of which are related to the damage variable D , which

increases with the evolution of damage according to [12]:

$$\dot{D} = \frac{L \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{pl}}{\bar{u}_f^{pl}} = \frac{\dot{\bar{u}}^{pl}}{\bar{u}_f^{pl}} \quad (7)$$

where L is the characteristic length, $\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}$ and \bar{u}^{pl} respectively are the equivalent plastic strain and equivalent plastic displacement. Before damage initiation $\dot{\bar{u}}^{pl} = 0$; after damage initiation $\dot{\bar{u}}^{pl} = L \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$. And \bar{u}_f^{pl} is the equivalent plastic displacement at failure computed as $\bar{u}_f^{pl} = 2G_f / \sigma_{y0}$, in which, σ_{y0} is the yield stress at the time when the failure criterion is reached, and G_f is the fracture energy per unit area:

$$G_f = \int_{\bar{\varepsilon}_0^{pl}}^{\bar{\varepsilon}_f^{pl}} L \sigma_y d\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl} = \int_0^{\bar{u}_f^{pl}} \sigma_y d\bar{u}^{pl} \quad (8)$$

in which, $\bar{\varepsilon}_0^{pl}$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}_f^{pl}$ respectively are the equivalent plastic strains at the onset of damage ($D=0$) and at final failure ($D=1$).

The experimental stress-strain curves show that the form of final failure is brittle instead of ductile no matter the epoxy is under uniaxial tension or compression, thus the fracture energy is given as a very small value of 0.5 J/m^2 , since a value smaller than this may induce numerical instability.

Fig.3. Stress-strain behavior of the matrix

2.3.2 Interface model

Interfacial debonding is included in the simulation by cohesive elements, with the constitutive response defined in terms of a bi-linear traction-separation law which relates the separation displacement between the top and bottom faces of the element to the traction vector acting upon it. The initial response is linear in absence of damage with an elastic stiffness of K :

$$t_n = K\delta_n, \quad t_s = K\delta_s, \quad t_t = K\delta_t \quad (9)$$

where t_n , t_s and t_t are the normal and the two shear tractions, respectively, δ_n , δ_s and δ_t are the corresponding separations. The elastic stiffness is selected as $K = 10^8 \text{ GPa/m}$, large enough to ensure the displacement continuity at the interface and to avoid any modification of the stress fields around the fibers in the absence of damage [4].

The maximum nominal stress criterion is used to predict the damage initiation of the interface, which is represented as:

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0}, \frac{t_s}{t_s^0}, \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\} = 1 \quad (10)$$

where t_n^0 , t_s^0 and t_t^0 represent the peak values of the nominal stress when the deformation is either purely normal to the interface or purely in the first or the second shear direction, respectively. $\langle \rangle$ is the Macaulay brackets, which return the argument if positive and zero otherwise, to impede the development of damage when the interface is under compression. As the strength of interface can hardly be measured by experiment, for simplicity, it is assumed to have similar mechanical properties with the matrix: the normal and the two shear strength of the interface are assumed to be equal to the tensile strength and the cohesion of the matrix, respectively, i.e., $t_n^0 = 80 \text{ MPa}$, $t_s^0 = t_t^0 = 103 \text{ MPa}$.

Once the damage begins, the traction stress is reduced depending on the interface damage parameter D , which evolves from 0 (in the absence of damage) to 1 (at ultimate failure), as shown in Fig.4. The displacement at failure (δ_n^f or δ_s^f) is determined by the fracture energy G , which corresponds to the area under the traction-separation curve. The interface fracture energy is taken from Ref. [3] as 100 J/m^2 .

Fig.4. Traction-separation law of the interface

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 In-plane shear

3.1.1 Stress-strain curves

The simulated in-plane shear stress-strain curves of the RVEs are shown in Fig.5, compared with the experimental result from [8]. As can be seen, the simulated results of all RVEs have very good consistency, with the elastic regimes of all the curves almost superposed. The different fiber distributions of RVEs cause very little difference in the simulated shear strength and failure strain, thus in return proves the RVE is large enough to represent the bulk material. The predicted in-plane shear strengths are a little smaller than the experimental value, but generally the errors are within 15%. The predicted in-plane shear failure strain also agrees well with the experimental result. Considering the uncertainties of the interface

properties, the accuracy of the numerical model is acceptable.

Fig.5. The simulated in-plane shear stress-strain curves and comparison with experiment [8]

Fig.6. Ultimate damage state of RVE under in-plane shear

3.1.2 Failure mechanism

Take RVE-1 for example, Fig.6 illustrates the ultimate damage state of the RVE under in-plane shear. As can be seen, a complete fracture surface is generated in the model, which runs through the fiber direction. To get a clearer understanding of the damage form, the model is broken up along the

fracture surface, showing the details of the fracture surface. It is interesting that the fracture surface is not parallel to the fibers, but has certain angle of inclination with the fiber direction. The actual value of the inclination angle is about 11°, which is approximately equal to the internal friction angle of the matrix (11.5°), indicating a leading role of the matrix plastic damage in the failure behaviour of the

composite. However, this exact inclination angle is not necessarily to form, as the crack propagation path will be affected by the distribution of fibers. It can also be seen that interfacial debonding only happens at the locales near the front and back surface, leaving the most of the fracture surface being matrix plastic damage. Thus it is concluded that damage first occurs in the form of interfacial debonding near the outer surface, and then matrix plastic damage is induced at the vicinity of the interface damage and propagates inward, finally, the matrix damage links as a complete surface that runs through the RVE, causing the ultimate fracture of the RVE.

3.2 Transverse shear

3.2.1 Stress-strain curves

The simulated transverse shear stress-strain curves are illustrated in Fig.7. As can be seen, the difference in fiber distribution causes more divergence in the stress-strain relation than in-plane shear, especially in the failure strain. And the

average transverse shear failure strain is smaller than the in-plane shear failure strain. This is probably because when the loading is along the longitudinal direction, more interface slipping is allowed to happen, for instance, in the form of fiber-matrix debonding or fiber pull-out.

Fig.7. The simulated transverse shear stress-strain curves

Fig.8. Damage initiation and evolution of RVE-1 under transverse shear

3.2.2 Damage initiation and evolution

The damage initiation and evolution process of the RVE under transverse shear is shown in Fig.8, with each damage state corresponding to one point in the stress-strain curve. Point a is the peak of the stress-strain curve, standing for the transverse shear strength of the composite, and the corresponding damage state is shown in Fig.8a. It is found that the main damage mechanism at this stage is matrix plastic damage, which occurs right near the interfaces of two adjacent fibers. At the same time, interfacial debonding can also be found between adjacent fibers, as can be seen more clearly by a partial enlarged drawing. And the connecting line of the two fibers is approximately parallel to the direction of maximum principal stress (i.e. 45° direction), thus the interfacial debonding is supposed to be caused by the maximum tensile principal stress.

After the peak point, the curve shows a slow declining period, at the same time more matrix damages happen at different locations where two fibers are close to each other, as shown in Fig.8b. Finally, matrix cracks are linked to form a main crack, passing through different interfaces in the path and causing the ultimate fracture of the composite, as shown in Fig.8c.

Fig.9 shows the ultimate damage forms of the other four RVEs. It is obvious that the fiber distributions greatly affect the crack propagation path. In most cases, a main crack that runs through the RVE will form; but when the fiber distribution is too disorderly, the throughout crack may fail to form, as is the case of RVE-2. This also gives the explanation to Fig.7 that why the stress-strain curve of RVE-2 deviates from the others.

Fig.9. Ultimate damage forms of different RVEs

4 Conclusions

The failure behavior of unidirectional FRPs subjected to in-plane and transverse shear is studied

using computational micromechanics. RVEs with different microscopic structures are constructed to consider the effect of random fiber distribution. The predicted in-plane shear stress-strain curves show

reasonable agreement with the experimental results. The microscopic damage mechanisms of the composite under both loadings are clearly revealed, showing complicated interactions between different damage forms involving matrix plastic deformation and interfacial debonding.

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